

Definition of the Intended Learning Outcomes per each stakeholder group

The Intended Learning Outcomes (ILO) define what a learner will acquire and will be able to do upon successfully completing their studies. It is the centrepiece of the definition of training or retraining curricula.

To introduce In Silico Trials several stakeholders require training and re-training. In the following, we map these stakeholders and list all possible ILO related to In Silico Trials. Then, we propose which ILO would be necessary for each stakeholder.

Stakeholder groups

A top-level distinction is between training provided to students pursuing a degree and re-training provided to professionals already working the job.

Training

Biomedical Engineering (MS, PhD)

Biomedical engineers (a.k.a. bioengineers or medical engineers) are the primary profile to train the next generation of experts in In silico Trials. They have the combination of technical skills and life science knowledge required. For this reason, elements of In Silico Trials should be taught in every MS degree of biomedical engineering.

It also makes sense to imagine a PhD focused on In Silico Trials. In this case it is not unusual for the PhD student to have, rather than an MS in biomedical engineering, an MS in physics, computer science, applied math, etc. In these cases, there usually a realignment with elements of human biology, physiology, and pathology. But for simplicity we will also refer these as PhD in Biomedical Engineering.

A special point should be made for the MS degrees in kinesiology (or motor science, or sport science). From country to country and sometime from university to university the curricula of these degrees vary considerably, ranging from quasi-life science degrees to quasi-engineering degrees. So, while the introduction of some In Silico Trials elements in these MS programs is desirable, the choice of ILOs should be done in the light of the specific curriculum adopted.

Medicine (MS)

Here we refer to the degree of medical doctor that depending on the countries may be organised as a monolithic degree or on a BS+MS scheme.

Life Science (MS)

With this class of stakeholders, we refer to all degrees at MS level that are related to human health. Thus, this includes, among the others, biology, pharmacology, biotechnology, but not veterinary science or botany. It also includes biomedical science, for those degrees focused on human health.

Allied Health professions (MS)

These are all the non-medical clinical degrees such as nursing, radiology technologist, physiotherapist, etc. While in some cases one can access to the clinical profession with a three year BS level degree, we believe that some knowledge of In Silico Trials may be useful only to those who pursue an MS degree in these disciplines.

Retraining

Here we make distinction between professionals who work in pre-competitive settings (academia, public research centres, etc.), in industry, and in governmental agencies.

Pre-competitive: Biomedical researchers

These are researchers working in pre-competitive settings on pre-clinical or clinical research on human health.

Pre-competitive: Health technology researchers

These are researchers working in pre-competitive settings on development, and validation of health technologies of all kinds. We include here also those working on Advanced Therapeutic Medical Products such as biologics, tissue engineering, etc.

Pre-competitive: Pharmacology researchers

These are researchers working in pre-competitive settings on the discovery, development, or pre-clinical and clinical testing of new pharmacological treatments.

Industry: Research and product development (R&D)

These are professionals working in industry on the development of new biomedical products. Their background can be quite heterogenous and differs depending on the type of product. Medical devices are usually developed by biomedical engineers, whereas pharmaceutical products are more likely developed by chemists, biologist, or pharmacologists.

Industry: Regulatory & Quality

These are professionals working in industry that work on the regulatory approval, the post-marketing monitoring, and the quality assurance of the production operations of biomedical products.

Governmental Agencies: Regulators staff

These are experts employed by governmental agencies (or in the case of EU notified bodies, even private organisations with a governmental mandate) that are involved with the regulatory evaluation and the marketing authorisation of biomedical products.

Governmental Agencies: HTA staff

These are experts employed by governmental agencies (supranational, national, regional, or otherwise) on the evaluation of the cost-effectiveness, indication, and reimbursability of biomedical products.

Intended Learning Outcomes

After completion of a training or re-training course, each stakeholder group will be able to achieve one or more of these skills:

H1. Apply the necessary preliminary technical and biomedical knowledge

These are the skills that students need to have as pre-requisite before they can receive the training targeting the skills listed in the other macro-skills. In most cases, they should be part of a previous degree (e.g., BS level) or of the foundational course of the current degree; however, in some cases, it might be necessary to include them in the curriculum a “Foundations on In Silico Medicine” module that fills some gaps.

H1.1. Math & Statistics

- H1.1.1. Define and review linear algebra and geometry problems
- H1.1.2. Solve linear algebra and geometry problems numerically
- H1.1.3. Define and review differential equations
- H1.1.4. Solve differential equations numerically
- H1.1.5. Define and review optimisation problems
- H1.1.6. Solve optimisation problems numerically
- H1.1.7. Use the concepts of probability, random variables, and probability distributions, to analyse, model, estimate and test hypotheses on data

H1.2. Physics & Chemistry

- H1.2.1. Use Newtonian mechanics laws to solve problems
- H1.2.2. Use thermodynamics and chemistry laws to solve problems
- H1.2.3. Use electromagnetism laws to solve problems

H1.3. Biomedicine

- H1.3.1. Apply knowledge of anatomy to the understanding of human pathophysiology
- H1.3.2. Knowledge of physics and chemistry to the understanding of human pathophysiology
- H1.3.3. Apply knowledge of pathophysiology to the understanding of the genesis, manifestations, and progression of human diseases
- H1.3.4. Apply knowledge of cell biology to the understanding of the mechanisms of action of drugs
- H1.3.5. Apply knowledge of biostatistics to the design, and analysis of clinical experiments

H1.4. Bioengineering

- H1.4.1. Select appropriate biomedical instrumentation to obtain the desired information
- H1.4.2. Select appropriate medical imaging instrumentation to obtain the desired information
- H1.4.3. Select appropriate in vitro diagnostic instrumentation to obtain the desired information
- H1.4.4. Elaborate bio-signals and medical images

- H1.4.5. Biophysics: apply physics laws to the solution of biomedical problems
- H1.4.6. Select appropriate experimental methods in vitro, or ex vivo to inform or validate in silico methodologies
- H1.5. Computer Science
 - H1.5.1. Program algorithms using interpreted programming languages and specialised libraries (Python, R, Matlab)
 - H1.5.2. Program algorithms using computationally efficient compiled programming languages and specialised libraries (C++, Fortran)
 - H1.5.3. Program algorithms to be batch-executed on time-sharing parallel or distributed computer systems (HPC, Cloud computing)
 - H1.5.4. Program algorithms for bioinformatics (sequence analysis, expression analysis, structural analysis, network analysis)

H2. Communicate about In Silico Methodologies

This macro-skill addresses the need for practitioners to accurately and effectively inform those stakeholders with direct or indirect decisional power on the use of in silico methodologies. We start with the skills to extract key concepts from experts, then collect and properly communicate concepts related to various aspects of in silico methodologies, then use these communication resources to influence specific stakeholder groups, and then extract requirements and specifications from stakeholders.

- H2.1. Extract key concepts from briefings provided by experts of in silico methodologies
- H2.2. Collect and use key concepts and definitions related to in silico methodologies in communication
- H2.3. Collect and use key concepts on safety and credibility of in silico methodologies in communication
- H2.4. Collect and use key concepts on economic risks and opportunities of in silico methodologies in communication
- H2.5. Collect and use key concepts on ethical risks and opportunities of in silico methodologies in communication
- H2.6. Collect and use key concepts on social risks and opportunities of in silico methodologies in communication
- H2.7. Collect and use a portfolio of success stories for in silico methodologies to achieve effective communication
- H2.8. Engage with and effectively communicate the benefits of in silico methodologies to the public and patients
- H2.9. Engage with and effectively communicate the benefits of in silico methodologies to policy-makers
- H2.10. Engage with and effectively communicate the benefits of in silico methodologies to medical professionals
- H2.11. Engage with and effectively communicate the benefits of in silico methodologies to biomedical researchers
- H2.12. Extract requirements and specifications for in silico methodologies from reports on unmet clinical needs

H3. Integrate in silico methodologies into legal, ethical and regulatory framework

This set of skills should enable the students to survey existing ethical, legal and regulatory frameworks and use them to define data management and to develop, validate and deploy in silico methodologies, including IRB submissions and the pursuit of regulatory objectives.

- H3.1. Survey the practice of in silico medicine concerning the relevant ethical principles
- H3.2. Survey the practice of in silico medicine concerning the relevant legislation
- H3.3. Develop data management plans for sensitive data with the help of cybersecurity and legal experts
- H3.4. Use the knowledge on specific topics in the development, validation, deployment and use (including post-market follow-ups) of in silico methodologies
 - H3.4.1. Use the knowledge of relevant technical standards
 - H3.4.2. Use the knowledge of risk management methodologies
 - H3.4.3. Use the understanding of the emerging legislation, standards, and guidelines on Artificial Intelligence
- H3.5. Pursue the approval of an Ethical Review Board for animal and human studies for the validation or the use of in silico methodologies
- H3.6. Use the knowledge of EU and US regulatory systems for medical products to achieve specific regulatory objectives
 - H3.6.1. Use regulatory knowledge to achieve the regulatory qualification of in silico methodologies
 - H3.6.2. Use regulatory knowledge to achieve the marketing authorisation for in silico methodologies
 - H3.6.3. Use regulatory knowledge to implement a total lifecycle-based framework for AI-based in silico methodologies

H4. Evaluate, select and use In Silico Methodologies according to their intended use

Here we list micro-skills required by anyone who needs to review, choose, and use in silico methodologies.

- H4.1. Evaluate the unmet need in terms of reduction, refinement, or replacement of in vitro, animal, or human experimentation
- H4.2. Conduct a critical review (SWOT analysis) of adopting different in silico methodologies to address an unmet need
- H4.3. Design the study involving in silico methodologies, define the Context of Use
- H4.4. Conduct risk analysis according to the ASME VV-40 or other relevant standards
- H4.5. Define the VVUQ plan according to ASME VV-40 or other relevant standards
- H4.6. Collect evidence of, or conduct, code verification
- H4.7. Conduct calculation verification
- H4.8. Conduct uncertainty quantification studies
- H4.9. Design validation experiments in vitro, on animals or on humans
- H4.10. Report credibility assessment of an in silico methodology according to ASME VV-40

- H4.11. Critically review a credibility assessment report
- H4.12. Position the adopted in silico methodology in the product life cycle
- H4.13. Conduct impact analysis on the deployment of in silico methodologies in a clinical setting
- H4.14. Use in silico methodologies to discover, develop/design, evaluate the safety and the efficacy, evaluate the cost-effectiveness of new candidate diagnostics or new interventions

H5. Develop In Silico Methodologies

Here we list the micro-skills required by practitioners of in silico methodologies that use them in the frame of a good simulation practice framework.

- H5.1. Translate unmet needs into specifications for an in silico trial solution
- H5.2. Develop data management methodologies respectful of ethical, legal, and procedural constraints
- H5.3. Develop synthetic clinical data collections from existing collections of clinical data
- H5.4. Select data-driven, knowledge-driven, or a combination of modelling methods based on the availability of annotated data and of reliable mechanistic knowledge on the mechanism of action of the class of diagnostics or interventions being modelled; on the natural history of the disease; on the underlying physiology
 - H5.4.1. Understand the capabilities and the requirements of Machine Learning models
 - H5.4.2. Understand the capabilities and the requirements of Deep Learning models
 - H5.4.3. Understand the capabilities and the requirements of Biochemistry models
 - H5.4.4. Understand the capabilities and the requirements of Biophysics models
 - H5.4.5. Understand the capabilities and the requirements of Agent-based models
 - H5.4.6. Understand the capabilities and the requirements of Stochastic models
 - H5.4.7. Understand the capabilities and the requirements of Optimisation models
- H5.5. Develop a data-driven model:
 - H5.5.1. Collect and properly organise data
 - H5.5.2. Curate data
 - H5.5.3. Choose the appropriate model or explore transfer learning
 - H5.5.4. Train the model
 - H5.5.5. Evaluate and tune the model on the training set
 - H5.5.6. Validate the model on test sets
- H5.6. Develop a knowledge-driven model:
 - H5.6.1. Collect and properly organise available mechanistic knowledge on treatment, disease, and physiology, using appropriate standards and tools
 - H5.6.2. Formulate the model in terms of inputs and outputs; identify patient-specific and population-specific inputs
 - H5.6.3. Formulate the model in terms of idealisations
 - H5.6.4. Formulate the mathematical model

- H5.6.5. Select the best numerical method to solve the mathematical model
- H5.6.6. Make or Buy – select the best tools to develop the model, also in the light of code verification
- H5.6.7. Collect and curate the input data
- H5.6.8. Develop all pre-processing steps to transform the available data into valid inputs, including the generation of virtual patients / virtual cohorts
- H5.6.9. Develop the model and run preliminary solution verification tests
- H5.6.10. Conduct parameters sweep and sensitivity analysis
- H5.6.11. Conduct initial validation to confirm the model's design choices

H6. Apply good simulation practice

The *good practice* are operational rules that usually emerge from a consensus process within a community of practice. However, in some cases they are formalised in voluntary or mandatory technical standards. As no standard exists yet for the Good Simulation Practice, we use as a basis the draft of the position paper on the Good Simulation Practice being developed by the In Silico World Community of Practice.

- H6.1. Find up-to-date guidelines, technical standards, and regulations related to good simulation practice
- H6.2. Apply best practices in data collection, data management, provision of synthetic datasets, data curation and processing
- H6.3. Develop documentation to describe and qualify for in silico methodologies
- H6.4. Apply Good Laboratory Practice and Good Clinical Practice to conduct laboratory or clinical validation studies
- H6.5. Manage all credibility assessment activities according to established good simulation practice
- H6.6. Assess, plan, implement and review good simulation practice
- H6.7. Use independent datasets (including synthetic) for calibration and validation